

Generalized Raking of Vectors*

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Abstract

The ordinary rake constrains data to a total of the same sign (exclusive of zeros) as the data. The ordinary rake fails when the data are of mixed sign (the plus-minus problem) or when the control is not the same sign as the sum of the data. This paper proposes a generalization of the ordinary rake to these situations. The objective is to control the data to a new total while preserving the structure of the data. The result is a weighted average of the ordinary raked values and the orthogonal projection of the data, viewed as a vector, onto the constant hyperplane generated by the control total. The generalized rake has similar properties to the ordinary rake. It lacks some of the weakness of the Akers-Siegel procedure. The cost is the nonuniqueness of a solution, which can also occur using the Akers-Siegel procedure.

1 Introduction

The problem of controlling a vector of data of mixed sign to a prescribed total, a.k.a. the (vector) plus-minus problem has been little studied. Only Akers and Siegel (1965) have addressed this problem. Whereas Akers and Siegel (1965) used an ad hoc approach to this problem, this paper addresses it mathematically using tools from geometry. Our solution avoids several of the problems associated with the Akers-Siegel technique at the cost of not having a unique solution. In many cases, the Akers-Siegel method also does not have a unique solution. Our solution is a weighted average of the ordinarily raked data, that is, the data multiplied by the ratio of the control total to the total of the data, and the orthogonal projection of the data onto the hyperplane generated by the control total. The actual solution is a simple affine transformation, similar to the ordinary rake. When nonzero data are of the same sign as the controls, the solution is the ordinary rate.

2 Ordinary Rake

The ordinary rake, also known as the proportionate rake, simply multiplies each element of a vector by the control value divided by the sum of the elements of that vector. Let vector \vec{x} be the initial vector. Let the control value be c . Let $b = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$, the sum of elements of \vec{x} . Finally, let vector \vec{x}' be the raked or transformed vector. Then,

$$x'_i = \frac{c}{b}x_i \text{ for all } i. \tag{1}$$

Throughout this section, we assume that c has the same sign as the nonzero elements of \vec{x} . In the interpretations of Subsection 2.1, these are assumed positive without loss of generality.

2.1 Geometric Interpretations

The ordinary rake can be viewed as a projection of the original vector onto the control hyperplane $\{\mathcal{H} \mid \mathbf{x} : \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = c\}$. A two-dimensional interpretation is shown in Figure 1. The thick gray arrow

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Figure 1: Vector Interpretation of Ordinary Rake

Figure 2: Ray Interpretation of Ordinary Rake

represents \bar{x} and the long, thin arrow represents \bar{x}' . Both vectors are collinear, lying on the same ray. In effect, the ordinary rake stretches or contracts \bar{x} until it contacts \mathcal{H} .

The second interpretation is based on drawing the ray defined by equation (1). We assume that $x_i \geq 0$ for all i . A nonpositive assumption would work as well. Figure 2 shows this ray. The arrow represents the ray of slope c/b . The linearity of this ray will aid the understanding of the generalized rake.

3 The Structure of the Transformed Data

The ordinary rake is monotonic and preserves the structure of the data in both order and ratio. That is,

$$c \geq b \Rightarrow x'_i \geq x_i \quad \forall i \neq 0 \text{ (monotonicity)}, \tag{2}$$

$$x_i > x_j \Rightarrow x'_i > x'_j \quad \forall j \neq i \text{ (order)}, \tag{3}$$

and

$$\frac{x_i}{x_j} = \frac{x'_i}{x'_j} \quad \forall j \neq i \text{ (ratio)}. \tag{4}$$

Monotonicity means that all nonzero data are shifted in the same direction as the change in their sum. The order property means that the ranking of the data is preserved. When the sign restrictions are relaxed, the ratio property must be lost to preserve the other two.

4 The Generalized Rake

The generalized rake removes the ordinary rake's assumption that the nonzero data and control are of the same sign, also known as the vector plus-minus problem. Any sign is permitted. The idea is to perturb the ordinary rake so as to preserve the order and monotonicity properties. The generalized rake is a weighted average of the ordinary rake and the orthogonal projection of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ onto \mathcal{H} :

$$x'_i = w \frac{c}{b} x_i + (1-w) \left(x_i + \frac{c-b}{n} \right) \quad \forall i. \quad (5)$$

The value of w can be determined heuristically. $w = 1$ reproduces the ordinary rake. $w = 0$ is the pure orthogonal projection, the only feasible solution for $b = 0$ and $c \neq 0$ or if no nonzero w is a feasible solution. The heuristic should aim to produce a high (but not the highest, as this leads to a corner solution) value of $w < 1$ to produce an acceptable trade-off between the two pure ($w = 0, 1$) solutions. A practical way to do this is to first check if $b = 0$, in which case the first division is infeasible, and set $w = 0$. Then, check whether the ordinary rake is feasible. If not, start with $w = 0.9$ and decrement w by 0.1 to $w = 0.1$ until the order conditions (3) are satisfied or $w = 0.1$ and conditions (3) are not satisfied. In the latter case, decrement from the lowest value of w tried (initially 0.1) by smaller amounts until a solution is obtained. If no such decrement works within a preset tolerance, set $w = 0$.

The generalized rake strengthens the monotonicity condition (2) to

$$c \geq b \Rightarrow x'_i \geq x_i \quad \forall i \quad (6)$$

Condition (6) allows the generalized rake to operate on zero data. Of course, if any zero data represent true zeros, they should be removed before raking.

4.1 Geometric Motivation for the Generalized Rake

Examination of the coordinates of the ordinary rake in Figure 1 shows that the order property (3) is maintained. Now, suppose that $x_1 < 0$ and $x_2 > 0$. Figure 3 shows the result of raking to the original control, using the vector interpretation of Figure 1. Letting $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R$ be the ordinarily raked version of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, Figure 3 shows that $x'_1 < x_1$, violating monotonicity. Therefore, the ordinary rake cannot be used for raking data of mixed sign.

Instead of multiplying the original data, addition may be used to make the data sum to c . The simplest additive transformation is the orthogonal projection, which adds a constant to each x_i :

$$x'_i = \left(x_i + \frac{c-b}{n} \right) \quad \forall i. \quad (7)$$

It is easy to show that equation (7) satisfies the monotonicity (6) and order (3) conditions. Let $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$ be the point defined by equation (7). Figure 4 graphically shows its construction. $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$ is constructed by adding the vector perpendicular to \mathcal{H} of length $(c-b)/n$ to $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$.

The generalized rake, given by equation (5) is, thus, a weighted average of the ordinarily raked vector $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$, the orthogonal projection of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ onto \mathcal{H} . Thus, $\bar{\mathbf{x}}'$ represents a compromise between $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$. The vector view of this compromise is shown in Figure 6 and further interpretations are made in Subsection 4.2. This compromise, however, is not unique. For any value of w that satisfies the order and monotonicity conditions, there exists some neighborhood $(w - \epsilon, w + \epsilon)$, ϵ small, such that these conditions remain true. In fact, this may be true of some very wide neighborhoods, or of asymmetric neighborhoods. The upshot is that no value of w uniquely satisfies the order and monotonicity conditions except for the special case of $b = 0$. Thus, the generalized rake lacks a unique solution. Moreover, combining observations changes the results, by changing the denominator in the fraction. The use of averages affects all methods that solve the plus-minus problem.

The corner solution is unique, at the cost of (strong) monotonicity. This is shown in Figure 5. In this solution, $x'_1 = x_1$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}'$ lies on the x_2 axis. In general, the corner solution has at least one i for which

Figure 3: The Ordinary Rake Applied to Data of Mixed Sign

Figure 4: Construction of the Orthogonal Projection

Figure 5: Generalized Rake Corner Solution

$x'_i = x_i$. If the strong monotonicity condition (6) is relaxed to permit this solution, then the generalized rake has exactly one solution, provided that the order conditions (3) are satisfied.

4.2 Geometric Interpretation of the Generalized Rake

Figure 6 shows the vector geometric interpretation of the generalized rake. Vectors $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R$ and $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P$ are as before. Vector $\bar{\mathbf{x}}'$ is the generalized rake using w . w can be understood through the identities

$$w = \frac{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R - \bar{\mathbf{x}}'\|}{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_P\|} \quad (8)$$

and

$$1 - w = \frac{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_P - \bar{\mathbf{x}}'\|}{\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}_R - \bar{\mathbf{x}}_P\|}, \quad (9)$$

where the norm is understood to be the usual Euclidean one.

Figure 7 shows the line interpretation of the generalized rake. It is very similar to the line interpretation of the ordinary rake shown in Figure 2. Instead of a ray of slope c/b , it is a line of slope wc/b . Instead of intersecting the x'_i axis at 0, it intersects it at $(1 - w)(c - b)/n$. This shifted intersect reflects the incorporation of the orthogonal projection. Of course, if $b = 0, c \neq 0$, the slope becomes 0 and the intersection occurs at $(c - b)/n$. If $c = 0, b \neq 0$, w becomes indeterminate so long as monotonicity is satisfied. If $b = c = 0$, there is no problem to solve, so $\bar{\mathbf{x}}' = \bar{\mathbf{x}}$.

5 The Akers-Siegel Procedure

The Akers-Siegel (1965) procedure, called by its authors the “plus-minus proportionate adjustment procedure” applies separate rakes to the positive and negative elements of $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$. For the positive elements, the rake is

$$r_+ = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| + (c - b)}{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|}. \quad (10)$$

For the negative elements, the rake is

$$r_- = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| - (c - b)}{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|}. \quad (11)$$

Figure 6: Vector Interpretation of the Generalized Rake

Figure 7: Line Interpretation of the Generalized Rake

Figure 8: Geometric Interpretation of the Akers-Siegel Procedure

Geometrically, these form a pair of rays, as can be seen in Figure 8.¹

When $|c - b| > \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|$, the Akers-Siegel procedure becomes infeasible, as either r_+ or r_- ceases to be positive. In practice, data of one sign either change sign or become all zero. Figure 9 depicts this situation. Geometrically, the problem arises because of the use of two rays: their angle is not fixed. Akers and Siegel (1965) suggest a workaround of adding a constant k to each x_i , applying their procedure, and, finally, subtracting out k from each x_i . In effect, \vec{x} is orthogonally projected onto the hyperplane defined by c and k ,² the Akers-Siegel procedure is applied to the projected vector, and the result is orthogonally projected onto \mathcal{H} . This process, however, produces a nonunique solution dependent on k .

6 Comparison of the Generalized Rake and the Akers-Siegel Procedure

Akers and Siegel (1965) recognized three weaknesses with their technique. One of these weaknesses is eliminated and another mitigated by the generalized rake, while nonuniqueness, a result of the third weakness, cease to be generated by the choice of another parameter.

These weaknesses are

1. Applying the Akers-Siegel procedure to a vector and a vector which has identical numbers of detailed entries for each element of the original vector produces different results for the original vector. For fixed w , this problem does not exist with the generalized rake, as can easily be shown mathematically. When the numbers of detailed entries are not equal for every element of the original vector, the generalized rake will also produce different results.
2. The Akers-Siegel procedure does not alter zeros. Mathematically, $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} r_+ = r_+ \neq r_- = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^-} r_-$. Two limits imply no limit, so zeros cannot possibly be altered as a result of the kink in the transformation. The generalized rake has no kinks and gives zeros the value $(1 - w)(c - b)/n$. That is, zeros are transformed according to the orthogonal projection onto \mathcal{H} .
3. When $|c - b| > \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|$, the Akers-Siegel procedure is infeasible on the original \vec{x} , as mentioned in Section 5, unlike the generalized rake which is always feasible. The workaround of translating the original \vec{x} , performing the Akers-Siegel procedure on the transformed vector, and translating back the

¹Note that no vector interpretation is possible.

²Formally, this hyperplane is described by $\{\mathcal{H} \mid \mathbf{x} : \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = c + k\}$.

Figure 9: Geometric Interpretation of the Akers-Siegel Procedure at Breakdown

results produces nonunique results. Different translations produce different results which depend on the value k . On the other hand, the generalized rake produces a unique solution for fixed w .

The generalized rake removes weakness #2 completely and #1 for large numbers of important cases. Weakness #3 also disappears for fixed w .

7 Example

The example in Table 1 compares the Akers-Siegel procedure to the generalized rake using real-world data. The White data from Judson and Popoff (2004, p. 71) Table C.11 are used. The "Preliminary" data are the unconstrained data. The Akers-Siegel data come from Judson and Popoff (2004) with $r_+ = 1.016141$ and $r_- = .983859$. The generalized rake with $w = 0.05$ is displayed in the last column with $wc/b = 0.0529222$ and $(1 - w)(c - b)/n = 49.459375$. w is close to 0 because of the large negative entries while the data are being increased. More extreme values are perturbed less as a result of the combination of a small proportionate rake and a small shift compared to a rake of approximately 1.

8 Conclusion

The generalized rake solves the vector plus-minus problem in an elegant way. It allows the constraining of data of mixed sign to a control of any sign, while preserving the structure of the data. Instead of, in effect, fitting a function with one kink to the data like the Akers-Siegel procedure, it is a linear transformation. It eliminates or mitigates several known problems with the Akers-Siegel procedure. zeros in the original data are handled without difficulty. The generalized rake always exists, unlike some cases of the Akers-Siegel procedure. These advantages are gained at the cost of nonuniqueness. Future research may be able to define an objective function which the generalized rake or a variant can optimize uniquely.

Table 1: Comparison of the Akers-Siegel Procedure and the Generalized Rake

Age	Preliminary	Akers-Siegel	Generalized Rake
All ages	14,253	15,086	15,086 ^a
0-4	1,792	1,821	1,847
5-9	5,502	5,591	5,568
10-14	4,190	4,258	4,252
15-19	3,242	3,294	3,301
20-24	-8,331	-8,196	-8,306
25-29	-9,836	-9,677	-9,815
30-34	5,102	5,184	5,166
35-39	3,220	3,272	3,279
40-44	2,239	2,275	2,295
45-49	1,595	1,621	1,649
50-54	1,325	1,346	1,378
55-59	1,322	1,343	1,375
60-64	1,232	1,252	1,285
65-69	1,370	1,392	1,423
70-74	800	813	852
75 and over	-511	-503	-463

^aThe displayed detailed data do not sum to the control due to rounding.

References

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